

LOW VISCOSITY PROCESSING TO FORM ELECTRICALLY CONDUCTIVE EPOXY RESIN COMPOSITES USING NOVEL HYBRID CNT- COATED SILICA PARTICLES

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ABSTRACT

Hybrid silica-multiwall carbon nanotube (CNT) particles were produced by the growth of nanotubes onto spherical, mesoporous silica gel particles using the floating catalyst chemical vapour deposition method. The rheological properties of epoxy resin suspensions of these hybrid particles (SG6_3) were studied compared to suspensions of discrete (non-grafted) CNTs in the same resin. The complex viscosity of suspensions containing up to 5 wt.% of SG6_3 (containing 1.68 wt.% of grafted CNT) remained essentially unchanged, whereas an increase of up to five orders of magnitude resulted upon the addition of 1.68 wt.% of non-grafted CNTs. Whilst rheological studies indicated that SG6_3 did not form a percolated network at addition levels of 5 wt.%, addition of only 2 wt.% (0.66 wt.% CNT) was found to form an electrically – conductive percolated network in an epoxy resin composite with conductivity $\sim 10^{-4}$ S/m.

INTRODUCTION

Carbon nanotubes (CNTs) are multifunctional reinforcements that can impart both improved thermal, mechanical and electrical properties to polymer composites. However, the potential benefits of nanotubes have been limited by the difficulty of dispersing nanotubes into the matrix and even at the lower loadings required for functional applications, careful control of the processing conditions is required. Approaches used to improve the dispersion of CNTs in polymer matrices include chemical functionalization, cutting of the nanotubes, in situ polymerization, and enhanced physical blending. An alternative method to that of mixing nanotubes directly into the matrix is to attach the nanotubes to host particles which are then introduced into the matrix to form hierarchical composites [1]. The aim of this study was to develop hybrid CNT-based particles that are: firstly, easily dispersed in polymer matrices to form stable electrically-conductive percolated networks, in that they are resistant to the shearing forces generated during polymer processing; and secondly do not generate a significant increase in the viscosity of the polymer matrix, another common problem encountered with CNT-polymer composites. The approach chosen to produce the hybrid system was the direct growth of nanotubes onto a spherical particulate silica substrate. A previous paper [2] presented the detailed study of CNTs grown on mesoporous silica gel particles by the floating catalyst chemical vapour deposition method (FC-CVD). This paper presents a study of the rheological and electrical properties of epoxy resin composites containing these hybrid silica-CNT particles.

EXPERIMENTAL

Hybrid particles (fig. 1) produced by growth of MWCNTs onto spherical silica-gel particles using CVD under optimized conditions were termed SG6_3 [1]. SG6_3 suspensions were prepared at room temperature using mechanical stirring (2000 rpm for one hour) at loadings of 0.5, 1, 2, and 5 wt.% in Araldite LY556 epoxy resin (CNT loadings of 0.17, 0.34, 0.66, and 1.68 wt.%, respectively). For comparison, suspensions (NC) containing non-grafted MWCNTs were prepared under the same conditions and at the same CNT wt.% using commercial MWCNTs (Nanocyl NC 7000). For the composites an amine hardener (Aradur XB 3473, Huntsman) was added to the mixtures at a weight ratio of 100: 23 (resin:hardener), as recommended by the manufacturer. Rheological tests were performed on a Thermo Scientific MARS II rheometer: for rotational mode, the shear rate ($\dot{\gamma}$) was increased stepwise (0.005 – 1000 s⁻¹) and held at each step for 60s; under oscillatory shear; a strain (γ) sweep (0.5 – 500 % strain) was first conducted to determine the linear viscoelastic region (LVR). Once this region was identified, frequency sweep testing (0.5 – 100 rad/s) was performed at a constant strain, within the LVR, of 1%. Impedance values of the composites were measured using an Impedance Analysis Interface/NumetriQ PSM1735. the composite plaques were cut into specimens of approximately 40 x 40 mm. After polishing, silver paint was applied on two opposing cut faces and wires connected to these electrodes using a conductive silver-loaded epoxy adhesive. At least five measurements were taken for each sample.

Figure 1: SEM image of a SG6_3 hybrid particle

Figure 2: SG6_3 and NC suspensions, left standing for 24 hours.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figure 3: Fitting of steady shear data. A SG6_3 (0.33 wt.% CNT) suspension fitted with the Bingham (yield-Newtonian) model (equation 1) and a 0.33 wt. % NC suspension fitted with the Herschel–Bulkley (yield-Power Law) model (equation 2)

Suspensions. Visual observation revealed striking differences between the SG6_3 and NC suspensions. For example, the former flowed easily from the jars in which they were mixed even when the loading was increased to 5 wt.% (equivalent to 1.68 wt. % of CNT). These suspensions were also quite stable and upon tilting the jars after standing for 24 hours no obvious sedimentation was observed. In contrast, a spatula was required to transfer all of the NC suspensions, even the lowest loading of 0.17 wt. %. In the case of 1.68 wt.% loading, in contrast to the equivalent SG6_3, the suspension did not fully flow to the bottom of the jar (fig. 2). **Steady shear** data for the epoxy resin and the SG6_3 suspensions showed essentially Newtonian behaviour. The data were fitted to the Bingham plastic (yield-Newtonian) model (equation 1) but all showed only very low yield stresses (≤ 0.09 Pa). In contrast, the viscosities of the NC suspensions were two orders of magnitude higher than the SG6_3 suspensions and showed behaviour indicative of a CNT network. Thus the flow curves of the NC suspensions also showed a much superior fit to the Herschel–Bulkley (yield-Power Law) model (equation 2) as shown in fig. 3.

$$\tau = \tau_y + \eta_p \dot{\gamma} \quad (1)$$

$$\tau = \tau_y + K\dot{\gamma}^n \quad (2)$$

where: τ_y is the yield stress and η_p is the plastic viscosity n and K are constants.

Dynamic shear data also show the advantages of grafting (Fig. 4). No elastic network forms in the SG6_3 suspensions and their complex viscosity remained constant and similar to the neat resin. In contrast the CNT in the NC suspensions interact strongly, creating an elastic network even at low loadings, and only 1.65 wt.% of CNT increases η^* at 1 rad/s by ≈ 5 orders of magnitude. This significant difference is emphasized in Figure 5 is a plot of relative complex shear viscosity, η^*_{rel} (ratio of suspension to that of the neat resin) for both suspensions as a function of CNT content, in which the presence of SG6_3 causes hardly no significant change in suspension viscosity up to the highest loading (1.65 wt. %).

AC response of the composites is shown in fig.6. For the non-grafted CNT - based composites specific conductivity, σ , remained constant for all loadings throughout the frequency range studied and the level of σ achieved increased as more CNT were added to the resin. It is apparent that the incorporation of SG6_3 also enhances the electrical conductivity of the resin. However, the ability of these hybrid particles to form a conductive network at low loading within the epoxy matrix is not as good as CNT. For example, the incorporation of 0.17 wt. % SG6_3 does not increase the σ of the neat resin while the addition of 0.17 wt. % CNT increased σ by more than six orders of magnitude. Figure 6 also shows that the σ value of the 1.65 wt. % SG6_3 based composite is slightly lower than that of the 0.17 wt. % CNT- based composite.

Figure 4: Frequency dependency of the complex shear viscosity (η^*) of NC and SG6_3 suspensions.

Figure 5: Relative complex shear viscosity, η_{rel}^* (ratio of suspension to that of the neat resin) for NC and SG6_3 suspensions as a function of CNT content.

Figure 6: Specific conductivity as a function of frequency for Nanocyl MWCNT and SG6_3 epoxy composites.

Rheological and electrical percolation thresholds (PT). G' data were fitted to determine the rheological PT of the NC suspensions (equation 3), which gave the critical loading as $p'_{CNT,G'} = 0.02$ wt.%. In contrast, the G' values for SG6_3 suspensions showed little change with loading and power law behaviour was not observed. PT fitting was also used to determine the critical loading for an insulator–conductor transition in the cured composites (equation 4). Fitting yielded critical loadings of 0.03 wt.% and 0.16 wt.% for NC–epoxy and SG6_3–epoxy composites (see fig. 7), respectively. Thus, whilst rheology showed that SG6_3 did not form a percolated network at levels ≤ 5 wt.%, addition of only 2 wt.% (containing 0.66 wt.% CNT) was found to form an electrically–conductive percolated network.

$$G' = G'_0 (p_{CNT} - p'_{CNT,G'})^{t_{rheo}} \quad (3)$$

G' is the storage modulus, G'_0 is the proportionality constant, p_{CNT} is the CNT loading, $p'_{CNT,G'}$ is the critical CNT loading (from G'), and t_{rheo} is the rheological exponential constant.

$$\sigma = \sigma_c (p_{CNT} - p'_{CNT,\sigma})^{t_{ele}} \quad (4)$$

σ is the specific conductivity of the composite, σ_c is the proportionality constant, $p'_{CNT,\sigma}$ is the critical CNT loading (from σ), and t_{ele} is the electrical exponential constant.

Figure 7: Semi log plot of specific conductivity SG6_3 – epoxy as a function of CNT content. The inset showing a fit to the equation derived from percolation theory (equation 4)

CONCLUSIONS

Regardless of the SG6nm_3 loading, the complex viscosity of the suspensions did not change; whereas incorporation of 1.65 wt. % non – grafted CNTs increased the viscosity value by up to five orders of magnitude. In rotational shear, the shear viscosity profile of suspensions containing grafted particle (for all loadings) followed closely that of the neat resin over a shear range of $0.1s^{-1}$ to $1000 s^{-1}$. In contrast, the incorporation of only 0.17 wt. % non – grafted CNT completely altered the flow behaviour with the shear viscosity increasing more than an order of magnitude at low shear rate. These differences are ascribed to the fact that SG6nm_3 particles are essentially spherical and contain relatively non – interacting CNTs, whilst the non – grafted CNTs are high aspect – ratio particles which exhibit strong inter – tube interactions. In addition, the grafted particles also formed electrically percolated network within composites at low loading. The study reported here demonstrated not only a simple and practical method to control the dispersion of CNT into resin matrices but also as a way to introduce CNTs into polymer matrices without changing their rheology profile.

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